

Derick Wood's Publications

This list of Derick Wood's publications has been collected from several sources; the bibliographic data have been verified and corrected or completed whenever possible. Technical reports or similar internal publications are not listed if the results of these were also published elsewhere; to generate a complete list of Derick's technical reports would be a major task. Electronic addresses of publications are only provided when the only means by which to access such a work is the internet.

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As Derick's publications span a vast variety of fields, we could not rely on just a few obvious sources, like the *Mathematical Reviews*, the *Zentralblatt für Mathematik und ihre Grenzgebiete* or the database at <http://www.informatik.uni-trier.de/~ley/db/index.html>, but needed to search many other printed and electronic sources as well. The search was concluded in the end of August, 2009.

1. D. Wood: *On Generalised Interpretive Schemes for Programming Languages*. PhD thesis, Leeds University, 1968.
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3. D. Wood: The theory of left factored languages. I. *Comput. J.* **12** (1969), 349–356.
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6. D. Wood: The normal form theorem – another proof. *Comput. J.* **12** (1969/1970), 139–147.
7. D. Wood: A generalised normal form theorem for context-free grammars. *Comput. J.* **13** (1970), 272–277. Erratum: **14** (1971), 326.

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10. D. Wood: Syntax-generated interpretation of programming languages. *Rev. Française Automat. Informat. Recherche Opérationnelle* **4**(Sér. B-2) (1970), 71–89.
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17. D. Wood: A note on bicoloured digraph grammar systems. *Internat. J. Comput. Math.* **3** (1973), 301–308.
18. D. Wood: A note on table look-up. *Nordisk Tidskr. Informationsbehandling (BIT)* **13**(2) (1973), 245–246.
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20. D. Wood: Some remarks on the KH algorithm for s -grammars. *Nordisk Tidskr. Informationsbehandling (BIT)* **13** (1973), 476–489.
21. G. Rozenberg, D. Wood: Generative models for parallel processes. *Comput. J.* **17** (1974), 344–348.
22. A. Walker, D. Wood: On bell trees, their implementation and properties. Technical Report 74-CS-4, Department of Applied Mathematics, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, 1974.
23. D. Wood: Bounded parallelism and regular languages. In G. Rozenberg, A. Salomaa (editors): *L Systems. Lecture Notes in Computer Science* **15**, 292–301, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1974.

24. R. D. Rosebrugh, D. Wood: Image theorems for simple matrix languages and n -parallel languages. *Math. Systems Theory* **8**(2) (1974/75), 150–155.
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26. D. Wood: The design of compilers (Notes for A. M. 4E4/6E3). Lecture Notes 75/1, Department of Applied Mathematics, McMaster University, Hamilton, Ontario, Canada, 1975.
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